

APPENDIX I: FGD GUIDE

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION GUIDE FOR PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCE USE AMONG INTER-STATE COMMERCIAL DRIVERS IN ILORIN METROPOLIS

What is a focus group discussion?

A Focus Group Discussion (FGD) is a method for collecting qualitative data from community individuals brought together to discuss a specific topic. Questions are open-ended, with the aim of stimulating an informal discussion with participants in order to understand their attitude, beliefs, fears, questions and information needs with regards to topic at hand: psychoactive drug use among commercial drivers.

For the purpose of this study, each FGD session will last between forty-five to sixty minutes.

Purpose

The purpose of this guide is to help the facilitators run a focus group discussion (FGD) with the aim of finding out more about the knowledge, attitude and use of psychoactive substances among interstate commercial drivers in Ilorin.

This FGD will also help facilitators better understand participant's perceptions on risky behaviours associated with use of psychoactive substances as commercial drivers.

Note for the facilitators:

- Avoid leading questions
- Remain neutral and do not react to participants' answers in order not to look or sound bias in the session
- Some of the questions are quite sensitive, ask them in a respectful manner and in line with the local culture, in which case, put into consideration the participant's tribe and religious inclination.
- The facilitator needs to be able to probe further based on the responses received or rephrase questions if participants do not understand them

Note for the Notetakers:

- Notetakers must be able to speak the local language to record the group discussion effectively.
- In addition to recording what is said during the group discussion, the notetaker should also record the behaviour of the participants (remarkable attitudes, spontaneous reactions, interactions among the participants, etc.).
- The notetaker should maintain confidentiality whilst recording the discussion by using letters or numbers to identify participants instead of names.

- The notetaker may decide to write only brief notes during the discussion but immediately after the interview, he or she should write the notes in detail so that all pertinent information is recorded.
- An effective notetaker should have good listening and writing skills
- You should be familiar with the list of questions and the topic of investigation
- Take notes in a comprehensive way but not literally
- Observe and remain impartial
- You may ask, with the consent of the facilitator, a participant to repeat their answer if they do not hear it the first time
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A. Introduction by facilitator (10minutes)

- **Welcome address:**

Respectfully recognize every participant.

- **Introduction of members:**

Introduce appropriately yourself, your notetaker and other members of your team.

- **Introduction of topic of FGD:**

Introduce the topic as 'Use of psychoactive substances among commercial drivers in Ilorin'. The purpose and objectives, and state how long the session would last.

- **Introduction of rules of FGD:**

Participants should respect each other's views, no direct personal attacks, no use of abusive words/phrases or other disruptive behaviours, participants may choose to leave the FGD at any time if they feel uncomfortable.

- **Clarifications:**

Allow for any clarifications concerning purpose of the FGD, rules, and what the data may be used for. Before commencing, ensure informed consent (verbally), ask permission to take notes and explain that confidentiality will be maintained throughout. Also explain clearly that participation in the FGD does not guarantee participants will receive any kind of special inducement or support from the team of facilitators.

To summarise the above, say introduction in the following way:

Good day sirs and mas, my/our name is/are_____.

We are a team of mental health practitioners from University of Ilorin Teaching Hospital, UITH. Do you know UITH? Many people here call it General hospital Oke-oyi.

We are here at your motor park to hear your opinions and views on psychoactive drug use. This is so we are able to use some of the information to provide you necessary health education on psychoactive drug use. Also, information provided will be used for research purposes.

- *Participation is free and there is no obligation to respond, you can stop at any point.*
- *No personal data will be shared with others and the information provided will be analysed anonymously and used confidentially.*
- *Your views are valuable and important, and will contribute to ensuring (i) we deliver a proper health education for you (ii) proper data analysis for research purpose.*
 - *You are advised to respect one and other's views/opinions and avoid abusive or any form of disruptive behaviours.*
 - *At the end of the discussion, we will try to answer your own questions about psychoactive drug use.*
 - *This group discussion will last between forty-five to sixty minutes.*
 - *Do you have any questions? Are you willing to participate in the group?*

B. Question guide for FGD with interstate commercial drivers in Ilorin on their use of psychoactive substance.

(Part B takes between 25 to 40minutes)

Name(code with initials): _____

Motor park: _____

Date: (DD/MM/YYYY) ____ / ____ / _____

Facilitator's name: _____

Group name/description: _____

Ages _____

Consent: Do you provide consent to document, use, store and share the information provided for reporting and other research purposes?

YES NO (if NO, say thanks and let the person leave)

If YES, Say may I begin now?

Question	Answer
<u>Knowledge of drug use</u>	
What do you understand by drug abuse?	
What are the common drugs of abuse you know?	
Are all drugs of abuse hard drugs?	

What are the consequences of drug use as it relates to driving?	
What are the other consequences that may not directly relate to driving?	
How can you identify someone that is addicted to drug use?	
Where is the best place to refer someone with drug use problems for treatment?	
<u>Attitude/Beliefs</u>	
In your opinion, do you believe drug addiction has a spiritual causation? Ask if 'yes', why? If 'no', what is/are cause(s) of addiction?	
In your opinion, is drug abuse a result of moral failing of the society? Ask if 'yes', why? If 'no', why?	
In your opinion, is drug abuse a sign of weakness? Ask if 'yes', why? If 'no', why?	
<u>Use of psychoactive substances</u>	
Do you take any psychoactive drug? Ask if 'yes', how often?	
What is your opinion about drinking/using psychoactive drugs while driving?	
How can you prevent drug use among drivers?	
How do you think you can help yourself or someone with drug use problems?	

C. Closing/ appreciation (10minutes)

To close, allow time for people to ask their own questions and explain again what happens with the data collected

Say, many thanks for their time and feedback! Explain how participants can contact the facilitator/researcher if they have any more questions or feedback.

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It is preferable for the facilitators and notetakers to carry out a Debrief together, and write up any additional information as soon as possible so that it is not forgotten.